

GLODS-SI-Mix: A Deterministic Direct-Search Method for Mixed-Variable Black-Box Optimization

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Abstract

We propose GLODS-SI-Mix, a deterministic direct-search method for bound-constrained mixed-variable black-box optimization with continuous, ordered discrete, and categorical variables. The method follows the classical search/poll structure of directional direct search and extends GLODS-SI from continuous variables to mixed-variable domains. As in GLODS, the algorithm maintains a list of active points, selects poll centers from this list, generates trial points through a poll step, and updates the list by comparison and merging. The new feature is that these operations are performed in a canonical search space, whereas objective-function evaluations are carried out only after reconstruction in the original variables.

The canonical state stores continuous variables as normalized coordinates, ordered discrete variables as indices, and categorical variables as permutation-invariant labels. A single step-size parameter α controls all poll moves: continuous variables are perturbed in normalized coordinates, while finite-valued variables are polled through ranks derived from α and the cardinality of the corresponding domain, with a cyclic cap for the categorical case. Categorical variables are handled by Deterministic Neighborhood Rotation (DNR), which rotates the active categorical ordering across epochs without imposing a fixed metric, artificial ordering, or preliminary learning phase.

The convergence statement follows the standard refining-subsequence route of direct search and is deliberately conservative. On stabilized continuous fibers, accumulation points satisfy first-order nonnegativity along feasible refining directions, inherited from GLODS-SI. The finite-valued components are treated through local rank-one neighborhood consistency statements at termination. The algorithm is fully deterministic, so each reported result corresponds to a single reproducible run. Experiments on the 16-problem Cat-Suite benchmark show competitive performance against CatMADS and three published baselines, while a 504-problem scaling study provides empirical evidence of scale invariance across eight orders of magnitude in heterogeneous scaling.

Keywords: Derivative-free optimization · Mixed-variable optimization · Direct search · Categorical variables · Scale-invariant algorithms · Deterministic optimization

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1 Introduction

We consider the bound-constrained mixed-variable black-box optimization problem

$$\min_{x \in \Omega} f(x), \quad \Omega = \Omega_C \times \Omega_D \times \Omega_K, \quad (1)$$

where f is available only through function evaluation, and derivatives are unavailable, unreliable, or too expensive to use [7, 10]. The feasible set is a Cartesian product of three types of variables: n_C continuous variables in a box Ω_C , n_D ordered discrete variables on finite numerical grids Ω_D , and n_K categorical variables taking values in finite unordered sets Ω_K . Such problems arise naturally in engineering design, system configuration, material selection, and operational decision-making, where real-valued parameters, finite technological choices, and qualitative alternatives must be optimized jointly.

Direct-search methods are well suited to black-box optimization because they use only function values. Their classical structure is organized around a *search* step and a *poll* step. The search step may explore the domain using any finite strategy, whereas the poll step performs a local exploration around a selected point, the *poll center*, using a step-size parameter and a set of polling directions. The poll step is the component on which the convergence analysis rests: a successful poll produces an acceptable improvement, while an unsuccessful poll triggers a reduction of the step size and hence local refinement.

The GLODS framework [11] follows this direct-search philosophy but is designed for global–local optimization. Instead of running a single local search from one incumbent, GLODS maintains a list of active points. Each active point represents a local direct-search process with its own step size and comparison radius. New points generated by the search or poll steps are compared with the existing list: if they are sufficiently far from all active searches, they may start a new local search; if they are close to an existing one, they may merge with it. This list-and-merging mechanism is the key difference between GLODS and a simple multistart strategy. Several local searches are launched, but searches that become sufficiently close are not pursued redundantly.

The scale-invariant version GLODS-SI [16] keeps the same global–local direct-search structure but changes where the search geometry is defined. Continuous variables are mapped to the normalized box $[0, 1]^{n_C}$; polling, distance comparisons, and merging are performed in this normalized space; and objective values are computed only after reconstruction in the original physical variables. Thus, the step size and the comparison radius acquire a dimensionless meaning, independent of physical units and variable ranges. The decisive point is structural: scale heterogeneity is removed by separating the space in which the search geometry is defined from the space in which the objective is evaluated. Mixed-variable heterogeneity, usually treated as a different difficulty, has the same origin—the conflation of these two spaces—and admits the same remedy.

The present paper extends this same principle from continuous variables to mixed-variable domains. The goal is not to replace the GLODS mechanism, but to make it operate on mixed variables without imposing an artificial common geometry. The list of active points, the selection of poll centers, the search/poll structure, the cache, and the merging mechanism remain those of a GLODS-type method. What changes is the space in which these operations are carried out.

The difficulty is that the three variable blocks in (1) do not share the same geometry. Continuous variables carry a natural local geometry and can be refined by arbitrarily small displacements. Ordered discrete variables carry an order, but only through a finite set of admissible levels; their numerical spacing should not by itself define the search

geometry. Categorical variables are purely nominal: they carry identity, but no intrinsic order, distance, or notion of “between”. A direct-search method for mixed variables must therefore define neighborhoods without forcing all variables into a single artificial metric space.

The central idea of this paper is to separate two roles that are usually conflated: the space where the search geometry is defined and the space where the objective function is evaluated. All polling operations, cache lookup, distance comparisons, and merging decisions are carried out in a *canonical search space*. In this space, each variable is represented in a canonical form adapted to its structure: a normalized coordinate for a continuous variable, an integer index for an ordered discrete variable, and an identity index for a categorical variable. Objective-function values are computed only after reconstruction in the original variables. Thus the black box is always evaluated in the original problem space, while the search logic acts on a representation in which step sizes, ranks, and comparison radii have a common dimensionless meaning.

This is the mixed-variable analogue of the GLODS/GLODS-SI construction. As in GLODS, the algorithm maintains an active list of points, selects poll centers from that list, generates trial points through search and poll steps, and updates the list by comparison and merging. The comparison radius still decides whether a new point starts an independent local search or merges with an existing one. The new feature is that the list entries, the cache, the poll operators, the distance comparisons, and the merging geometry are expressed in the canonical mixed-variable space. When no ordered discrete or categorical variables are present ($n_D = n_K = 0$), this construction reduces exactly to GLODS-SI on the normalized continuous box.

The treatment of categorical variables follows the same separation principle. A categorical index is used only as a canonical identity for storage, reconstruction, comparison, and cache lookup; it is not interpreted as an ordinal coordinate. Local categorical polling is generated instead by *Deterministic Neighborhood Rotation* (DNR). At each epoch, a deterministic permutation induces a temporary cyclic neighborhood on the categorical identities, and this neighborhood changes over time according to a deterministic schedule. The permutation determines only which categorical alternatives are polled from the current identity; it never changes the identity of a stored point. Consequently, categorical alternatives are explored deterministically without imposing a fixed categorical metric, a permanent artificial order, or a preliminary learning phase, and all cached evaluations remain valid across permutation rotations.

Existing mixed-variable direct-search methods differ mainly in how they handle finite-valued and categorical variables. Early extensions of MADS to mixed variables use user-defined neighborhoods or problem-dependent mappings [4, 1]. Other derivative-free approaches for mixed-integer or mixed-variable optimization rely on prescribed neighborhood structures or randomization [14, 13, 12]. More recently, CatMADS [5] constructs categorical neighborhoods from problem-specific distances, possibly learned from an initial design of experiments. This provides a principled metric-based framework, but it uses an explicit categorical distance and requires either user-supplied or learned categorical structure. The present approach takes a different position: categorical values remain purely nominal, and deterministic exploration is obtained by rotating temporary neighborhoods rather than by imposing or learning a persistent metric. Table 1 summarizes how the present method relates to these approaches.

The resulting method, denoted GLODS-SI-Mix, is a deterministic direct-search algorithm for single-objective mixed-variable black-box optimization. Its poll step is driven by

Table 1: Comparison of representative direct-search methods for mixed-variable optimization.

Method	Deterministic	No categorical distance	No learning	Unified α
Audet & Dennis [4]	✓	×	✓	×
Abramson et al. [1]	×	✓	✓	×
Lucidi et al. [14, 13, 12]	×	✓	✓	×
CatMADS [5]	✓	×	×	×
GLODS-SI-Mix (this work)	✓	✓	✓	✓

a single step-size parameter α . For continuous variables, α is a normalized displacement in $[0, 1]$. For ordered discrete variables, α is converted into an integer rank proportional to the number of admissible levels. For categorical variables, the same rank rule is used within the active DNR permutation, with a cyclic cap to avoid redundant cyclic moves. Thus, the same scalar parameter controls continuous displacements, ordered discrete rank moves, and categorical permutation-induced moves.

The convergence statement is deliberately conservative. The analysis follows the classical refining-subsequence route of directional direct search and concerns the poll step only. On subsequences where the finite-valued variables stabilize, the method reduces to a GLODS-SI-type coordinate direct search on a continuous fiber. Accumulation points then satisfy first-order nonnegativity along feasible refining directions of that fiber. The finite-valued components are treated through local rank-one neighborhood consistency statements at termination. We do not claim global optimality, full Clarke stationarity on the full mixed-variable product space, or a complete finite-domain optimality theory.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows.

1. We propose a mixed-variable extension of the GLODS/GLODS-SI active-list and merging framework. Polling, cache lookup, distance comparisons, and merging are performed in a canonical mixed-variable search space, while objective values are evaluated only after reconstruction in the original variables.
2. We introduce a unified single-parameter poll mechanism. The same step-size parameter α generates normalized continuous displacements, rank moves on ordered discrete variables, and permutation-induced rank moves on categorical variables, without separate step-size bookkeeping per variable block.
3. We provide a deterministic treatment of categorical variables based on the separation between categorical identity and categorical locality. Category identities are fixed and used for storage, reconstruction, comparison, and cache lookup, while local neighborhoods are induced temporarily by deterministic permutation schedules. The resulting DNR mechanism explores categorical alternatives without imposing a fixed metric, a permanent ordering, or a preliminary learning phase; the two schedules used here are covering cycles with finite-window coverage (Proposition 1) and Sobol-rank with asymptotic non-exclusion (Proposition 2).
4. We give a conservative convergence certificate (Theorem 1) in the classical refining-subsequence style of direct search. On stabilized continuous fibers, accumulation points satisfy first-order nonnegativity along feasible refining directions inherited from GLODS-SI; finite-valued components are treated through rank-one neighborhood consistency statements at termination.

5. We report a fully deterministic computational study. On the 16-problem Cat-Suite benchmark of [5], GLODS-SI-Mix is compared with CatMADS and three published baselines. A 504-problem scaling study further evaluates parameter sensitivity and provides empirical evidence of scale invariance across eight orders of magnitude in heterogeneous scaling.

A broader geometric interpretation of canonical mixed-variable spaces and transient categorical geometry is developed separately in [17]. The combinatorial details of the DNR construction are expanded in the companion note [15]. Neither reference is required to follow the algorithm or the computational results of the present paper.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 states the mixed-variable problem and defines the canonical search space and reconstruction map. Section 3 develops the search/poll structure, the unified rank, and the variable-wise poll operators. Section 4 presents categorical polling and the two deterministic DNR schedules. Section 5 gives the complete GLODS-SI-Mix algorithm and the optional deterministic search step. Section 6 states the convergence certificate and its limitations. Section 7 reports the computational study. Section 8 concludes.

2 Mixed-variable problem and canonical representation

2.1 Mixed-variable problem

We consider the bound-constrained black-box optimization problem

$$\min_{x \in \Omega} f(x), \quad \Omega = \prod_{i=1}^n \Omega_i, \quad (2)$$

where the objective value is available only through function evaluation. The component domains Ω_i are of three possible types:

$$\Omega_i \in \{[l_i, u_i] \subset \mathbb{R}, \ell_i < u_i, V_i = \{v_{i,1} < \dots < v_{i,N_i}\}, K_i = \{c_{i,1}, \dots, c_{i,m_i}\}\}. \quad (3)$$

These correspond, respectively, to continuous variables, ordered discrete variables, and categorical variables. The continuous variables have a natural local geometry, the ordered discrete variables have an order but only finitely many admissible values, and the categorical variables carry identity only: no order or metric is assumed on K_i .

Let I_C , I_D , and I_K denote the corresponding index sets, with cardinalities n_C , n_D , and n_K , so that $n = n_C + n_D + n_K$. For a finite-valued variable we use

$$M_i = \begin{cases} N_i, & i \in I_D, \\ m_i, & i \in I_K, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

to denote the number of admissible levels. The set Ω is compact, and the objective $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is assumed bounded below. Additional regularity assumptions needed for the convergence statement are imposed only on continuous fibers in Section 6.

2.2 Canonical search space

GLODS-SI-Mix separates the space where the search geometry is defined from the space where the objective function is evaluated. The algorithm does not poll directly in the

original variables x . Instead, it works with a canonical state

$$\xi = (y, k, h),$$

whose three blocks are represented as follows:

- $y = (y_i)_{i \in I_C} \in [0, 1]^{n_C}$ stores normalized continuous coordinates;
- $k = (k_i)_{i \in I_D}$ stores ordered discrete indices $k_i \in \{1, \dots, N_i\}$;
- $h = (h_i)_{i \in I_K}$ stores categorical identity indices $h_i \in \{1, \dots, m_i\}$.

Thus the canonical search space is

$$\Xi = [0, 1]^{n_C} \times \prod_{i \in I_D} \{1, \dots, N_i\} \times \prod_{i \in I_K} \{1, \dots, m_i\}. \quad (5)$$

For continuous variables, the canonical coordinate is the affine normalization

$$y_i = \frac{x_i - \ell_i}{u_i - \ell_i}, \quad i \in I_C. \quad (6)$$

For ordered discrete variables, the canonical coordinate is the index k_i , not the numerical value v_{i,k_i} . For categorical variables, the canonical coordinate is the identity index h_i , not a position in any categorical ordering. This distinction is essential: the categorical index is used for point identity and cache lookup, whereas the temporary orderings used by DNR affect only the poll neighborhood.

2.3 Reconstruction and objective evaluation

Objective values are computed only after reconstruction in the original variables. The reconstruction map $\Psi : \Xi \rightarrow \Omega$ is defined componentwise by

$$\Psi(\xi)_i = \begin{cases} \ell_i + (u_i - \ell_i) y_i, & i \in I_C, \\ v_{i,k_i}, & i \in I_D, \\ c_{i,h_i}, & i \in I_K. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Thus the value associated with a canonical state ξ is $f(\Psi(\xi))$.

Lemma 1 (Bijectivity of the reconstruction). *Assume that all values listed in each ordered discrete set V_i and each categorical set K_i are distinct. Then the reconstruction map $\Psi : \Xi \rightarrow \Omega$ defined in (7) is a bijection.*

Proof. For each continuous coordinate, the affine map $y_i \mapsto \ell_i + (u_i - \ell_i)y_i$ is a bijection from $[0, 1]$ to $[\ell_i, u_i]$. For each ordered discrete or categorical coordinate, reconstruction is an index-to-value lookup between two finite sets of the same cardinality. The Cartesian product of these componentwise bijections is a bijection from Ξ to Ω . \square

For analysis, we may regard $f \circ \Psi$ as the objective induced on Ξ , but the black box is always called in the original variables. In particular, the objective is never interpreted as a function to be evaluated on categorical indices or on the normalized coordinates themselves.

2.4 Canonical cache and invariance under DNR

Mathematically, evaluated points are identified by their canonical state ξ . The cache therefore records pairs of the form

$$(\xi, f(\Psi(\xi))).$$

This has two consequences. First, continuous cache comparisons are performed in normalized coordinates, so they are insensitive to physical units and variable ranges. Second, categorical cache keys are invariant under deterministic neighborhood rotation: when the active categorical permutation changes, the category with canonical identity h_i remains the same category, even if its position in the active permutation changes. The DNR mechanism changes only which categorical alternatives are polled from the current state; it never changes the identity of a stored point.

This separation is the reason why polling, distance comparisons, merging, and cache lookup can be carried out in the canonical search space, while objective values are still evaluated in the original mixed-variable domain.

In the theoretical description, cache matching is exact in the canonical state space Ξ . In the implementation, finite-valued variables are stored through their equivalent normalized grid representatives in $[0, 1]^n$, but these representatives are obtained deterministically from the same indices k_i and h_i . This is an implementation device only; the mathematical state remains $\xi = (y, k, h)$. Further details are given in Appendix C.

2.5 Initialization

Initial trial states are generated in the canonical space. A point $u \in [0, 1]^n$ is converted componentwise into a canonical state by setting

$$y_i = u_i \quad (i \in I_C),$$

and, for finite-valued variables, by rounding to the nearest admissible index:

$$\begin{aligned} k_i &= 1 + \text{round}(u_i(N_i - 1)), & i \in I_D, \\ h_i &= 1 + \text{round}(u_i(m_i - 1)), & i \in I_K. \end{aligned}$$

The resulting indices are clipped if needed to remain in their admissible sets. The numerical experiments use a deterministic initialization based on Sobol points augmented with axial vertices and the center; the full implementation details are given in Appendix C.

2.6 Reduction to GLODS-SI

The construction reduces exactly to the continuous GLODS-SI framework when no finite-valued variables are present.

Remark 1 (Reduction to GLODS-SI). *If $n_D = n_K = 0$, then the canonical state is simply $\xi = y \in [0, 1]^{n_C}$ and the reconstruction map (7) reduces to*

$$\Psi(y)_i = \ell_i + (u_i - \ell_i) y_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, n_C.$$

The mixed poll operators of Section 3 reduce to projected coordinate poll moves in the normalized box $[0, 1]^{n_C}$. Hence GLODS-SI-Mix coincides with GLODS-SI [16] in the continuous-only case, and the continuous refining-direction stationarity result used in Section 6 is inherited from that setting.

3 Search/poll structure and poll operators

GLODS-SI-Mix is a directional direct-search method that operates in the canonical space Ξ . This section develops the poll step, which is the component used in the convergence certificate. We first describe the search/poll structure that a direct-search reader will recognize (Section 3.1); the mixed-variable content—a unified rank (Section 3.2) and the variable-wise poll operators (Section 3.3)—is introduced only afterwards, and the full poll set is assembled in Section 3.4.

3.1 Search/poll structure

At each iteration the algorithm selects a poll center $\xi^* = (y^*, k^*, h^*)$ from the active list and polls along the maximal positive basis

$$D = [I_n \mid -I_n], \quad (8)$$

whose $2n$ columns are the signed unit vectors $\{\pm e_1, \dots, \pm e_n\}$. Each column identifies a coordinate $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ to perturb and a sign $s \in \{+1, -1\}$. For a selected poll center, a single scalar step-size parameter α controls the poll moves of all variable types. In the continuous block it is a normalized displacement; in the finite-valued blocks it is converted into a rank through the relative-resolution rule of Section 3.2.

The trial point generated along (i, s) at step size α is

$$\xi^{\text{trial}} = E_i(\xi^*, T_i(\xi^*, s, \alpha)), \quad (9)$$

where $E_i(\xi, z) = (\xi_1, \dots, \xi_{i-1}, z, \xi_{i+1}, \dots, \xi_n)$ replaces component i of ξ by z , and T_i is the variable-type-dependent poll operator of Section 3.3. The poll therefore generates at most $2n$ trial points, collected in the poll set $P(\xi^*; \alpha)$ of Section 3.4. Each trial is evaluated through $f(\Psi(\cdot))$, with Ψ from (7), unless it is already in the cache.

The poll is *successful* if at least one evaluated trial point is accepted by the merge mechanism, and *unsuccessful* otherwise. Accepted trials are merged into the active list by the GLODS list mechanism. The step size is updated by

$$\alpha \leftarrow \begin{cases} \gamma \alpha, & \text{on a successful poll,} \\ \beta \alpha, & \text{on an unsuccessful poll,} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

with $\gamma \geq 1$, $\beta \in (0, 1)$; the numerical experiments use $\beta = 1/2$ and $\gamma = 2$. Termination is governed by a threshold α_{\min} , discussed in Section 6. When $n_D = n_K = 0$ this loop is exactly the GLODS-SI poll in $[0, 1]^{n_C}$ (Remark 1); the only mixed-variable ingredient is the operator T_i , developed next.

3.2 Unified rank

For finite-valued variables the poll reach is an integer rank derived from α and the domain size M_i . The ordered discrete and categorical cases differ only by an upper cap on the categorical rank, needed for the cyclic neighbor operator ν_i of Section 4 to be well defined:

$$r_i(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \max(1, \text{round}(\alpha(M_i - 1))), & i \in I_D, \\ \min(\lfloor M_i/2 \rfloor, \max(1, \text{round}(\alpha(M_i - 1))))), & i \in I_K. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The categorical cap $\lfloor M_i/2 \rfloor$ reflects the cyclic structure of the active permutation. Ranks larger than half the cycle do not define new cyclic separations, since they repeat positions already reachable by smaller ranks in the opposite direction. The cap is therefore a redundancy control, not an additional metric assumption. When M_i is even and $r_i = M_i/2$, the forward and backward moves lead to the same opposite category. Thus $\lfloor M_i/2 \rfloor$ is the largest geometrically meaningful rank (see the cyclic-collision example in Appendix A). In the typical regime $\alpha \leq 1/2$ with $M_i \geq 3$, the cap is inactive and the two branches coincide with the same relative-rank rule.

The rule has a relative-resolution interpretation. For continuous variables the displacement is exactly $\Delta y_i = \pm\alpha$. For finite-valued variables, except for rounding and the categorical cyclic cap, the rank satisfies $r_i/(M_i - 1) \approx \alpha$. Thus a rank- r_i move covers approximately the fraction α of the ordered domain, independently of its cardinality, giving α the common interpretation as the fraction of the native domain explored. The rank and clamp depend on the domain only through the index k_i , not through the values $v_{i,1}, \dots, v_{i,N_i}$. As $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, all variable types reach their finest admissible resolution at once: continuous steps vanish and $r_i = 1$ for every finite-valued variable.

Remark 2 (Unified step-size parameter). *A single scalar α serves as the step size for every variable type. There is no separate integer increment or categorical rank parameter to schedule independently: r_i is recomputed from α at each iteration through (11), and the update (10) acts on the same α for all types.*

3.3 Variable-wise poll operators

The poll operator $T_i(\xi^*, s, \alpha)$ takes one of three explicit forms:

$$T_i(\xi^*, s, \alpha) = \begin{cases} \Pi_{[0,1]}(y_i^* + s\alpha), & i \in I_C, \\ \text{clamp}(k_i^* + s r_i, 1, N_i), & i \in I_D, \\ \nu_i(h_i^*, s r_i), & i \in I_K, \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where r_i is given by (11), $\Pi_{[0,1]}(z) = \min(\max(z, 0), 1)$ is projection onto the unit interval, and $\text{clamp}(z, a, b) = \min(\max(z, a), b)$ is its integer-domain counterpart, so the discrete update advances the index k_i^* by $\pm r_i$ positions and truncates at the endpoints $\{1, N_i\}$. The categorical operator $\nu_i(h_i^*, \delta)$ returns the category whose position in the active DNR permutation is δ cyclic steps from that of h_i^* ; the poll uses $\delta = s r_i$, i.e. the rank- r_i forward neighbor when $s = +1$ and the rank- r_i backward neighbor when $s = -1$. The construction of the active permutation is deferred to Section 4.

Boundary handling. The three types use type-specific feasibility mechanisms. Continuous variables use the projection $\Pi_{[0,1]}$; ordered discrete variables use the structurally identical clamp on the integer domain; categorical variables need no boundary treatment, because the cyclic structure of the DNR permutation makes $\nu_i(h_i^*, s r_i)$ always a valid category index. Near a continuous or discrete boundary, projection or clamping may map two opposite trials to the same point; the cache detects the coincidence and avoids a redundant evaluation. The same mechanism handles the categorical case in which the cyclic wrap maps the two opposite neighbors to one category (when m_i is even and $r_i = m_i/2$). Worked numerical examples for the three boundary cases are given in Appendix A.

3.4 Poll set

For a poll center ξ^* and step size α , the poll set is

$$P(\xi^*; \alpha) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \bigcup_{s \in \{+1, -1\}} \{E_i(\xi^*, T_i(\xi^*, s, \alpha))\}. \quad (13)$$

Each $\xi^{\text{trial}} \in P(\xi^*; \alpha)$ differs from ξ^* in exactly one component, and is evaluated through $f(\Psi(\xi^{\text{trial}}))$ unless already cached. The generation of poll candidates is therefore fully described by the trial map (9), the poll set (13), and the step-size update (10); acceptance and list updates are handled by the GLODS merge mechanism described in Section 5. Worked enumerations of $P(\xi^*; \alpha)$ on three specializations (continuous-only, categorical-only, and a fully mixed case), and an illustration of how the DNR permutation rotates the active neighbors of a fixed canonical state, are given in Appendix D.

Example 1 (One mixed poll step). *Consider a mixed state with one variable of each type,*

$$\xi^* = (y_1^*, k_2^*, h_3^*) = (0.40, 7, 3),$$

with step size $\alpha = 0.10$. Variable 1 is continuous, variable 2 is ordered discrete with $N_2 = 100$, and variable 3 is categorical with $m_3 = 5$ and active permutation $p_3 = (3, 1, 5, 2, 4)$. The unified rank rule gives

$$r_2 = \max(1, \text{round}(0.10(100-1))) = 10, \quad r_3 = \min(2, \max(1, \text{round}(0.10(5-1)))) = 1.$$

The six poll candidates are

$$\begin{aligned} &(0.50, 7, 3), & (0.30, 7, 3), \\ &(0.40, 17, 3), & (0.40, 1, 3), \\ &(0.40, 7, 1), & (0.40, 7, 4). \end{aligned}$$

The first pair are continuous displacements by $\pm\alpha$ in normalized coordinates. The second pair are discrete rank-10 moves, the negative one clamped to the lowest index. The third pair are categorical rank-1 neighbors in the active permutation: since $h_3^ = 3$ sits at position 1 of p_3 , its two cyclic neighbors are the canonical indices 1 and 4. A single scalar α thus drives a continuous step, a discrete rank move, and a categorical permutation-induced move simultaneously, as summarized in Figure 1.*

In general, boundary projection, discrete clamping, categorical cyclic collisions, or previous cache entries may reduce the number of new function evaluations associated with a poll set.

4 Categorical polling and Deterministic Neighborhood Rotation

The categorical poll operator $\nu_i(h_i^*, sr_i)$ of (12) requires an active permutation of the category set. This is the point at which categorical variables differ fundamentally from continuous and ordered discrete variables. Continuous variables have a built-in notion of locality through small displacements, and ordered discrete variables have one through small changes of rank. Categorical variables have none: they carry identity, but no order,

Figure 1: One mixed poll step in GLODS-SI-Mix. The same step-size parameter α drives a continuous displacement, a discrete rank move, and a categorical permutation-induced move; the three blocks contribute their trials to the poll set $P(\xi^*; \alpha)$ (Example 1).

distance, or notion of “between”. A neighborhood for polling must therefore be supplied by the algorithm.

Using one fixed categorical neighborhood throughout the run would reintroduce an arbitrary structure. It would also create permanent blind spots: two categories that are never adjacent in that fixed neighborhood could never be compared by a rank-one categorical poll move. Deterministic Neighborhood Rotation (DNR) removes this dependence without committing to a permanent metric. The active permutation that defines the categorical neighborhood is rotated across epochs by a deterministic schedule, so the adjacency structure changes over time while the canonical identity h_i —the cache key (Section 2.4)—remains fixed.

The purpose of this section is to make this mechanism precise and to certify that it does not permanently exclude categorical alternatives from local polling. In this sense, the coverage properties below play for categorical variables a role analogous to the positive-spanning property of polling directions in continuous direct search: they ensure that the local exploration mechanism is not structurally blind. These are schedule-level properties. They justify the categorical locality used by the poll, while the convergence certificate itself is stated later in Section 6.

Two schedules are kept in the body. The covering-cycles schedule (Section 4.2) gives the stronger, tight finite-window guarantee: every pair of categories is cyclically adjacent within a bounded number of epochs. The Sobol-rank schedule (Section 4.3) gives the weaker asymptotic guarantee that no pair is permanently excluded, in exchange for greater categorical diversity per epoch. The two are interchangeable inside the algorithm (Section 4.4); the numerical experiments of Section 7 use Sobol-rank. A third schedule, affine, of practical interest when the categorical cardinality is very large, together with a cost comparison, is given in Appendix B.

4.1 Permutation-induced neighbors

Let $p_i^{(e)}$ be the active permutation of $\{1, \dots, m_i\}$ for categorical variable i at epoch e , interpreted cyclically. If $p_i^{(e)}(j) = h$, so that j is the position of canonical category h in the active permutation, then for an integer displacement δ the permutation-induced neighbor is

$$\nu_i(h, \delta) = p_i^{(e)}(1 + ((j + \delta - 1) \bmod m_i)). \quad (14)$$

This is exactly the operator used by the poll: the categorical row of (12) is $T_i(\xi^*, s, \alpha) = \nu_i(h_i^*, s r_i)$, so $\delta = +r_i$ gives the forward rank- r_i neighbor and $\delta = -r_i$ the backward one. The displacement δ measures cyclic distance in $p_i^{(e)}$ and the cyclic wrap is automatic; the largest meaningful magnitude is $\lfloor m_i/2 \rfloor$, as discussed in Section 3.2. The position j is obtained by the inverse lookup $j = (p_i^{(e)})^{-1}(h)$. Crucially, ν_i returns a canonical category identity, not a position: the active permutation determines which identities are neighbors, never the identity of a stored point; Figure 2 illustrates these permutation-induced neighbors.

Canonical identity h_i^* is invariant across epochs; the position $j = (p_i^{(e)})^{-1}(h_i^*)$ depends on the active permutation.

Figure 2: Permutation-induced rank- r_i categorical neighbors. The cache key is the canonical category index h_i^* , not its position j in the active permutation $p_i^{(e)}$. When $p_i^{(e)}$ rotates at an epoch boundary, j updates but h_i^* and all cached evaluations remain valid.

Within outer iteration t the active permutation is $p_i^{(e)}$ with epoch counter

$$e(t) = \left\lfloor \frac{t-1}{E} \right\rfloor, \quad (15)$$

so the permutation is fixed within an epoch and updated only at epoch boundaries; the numerical experiments use $E = 20$.

4.2 Covering-cycles schedule

The first schedule cycles deterministically through a finite family of cyclic orderings that jointly cover every unordered pair of categories.

Definition 1 (Covering-cycles schedule). *For a categorical variable with $m \geq 3$ levels, let $M = \lceil (m-1)/2 \rceil$, and let $\{\sigma^{(1)}, \dots, \sigma^{(M)}\}$ be a family of cyclic orderings of $\{1, \dots, m\}$ such that every unordered pair $\{a, b\}$ appears as cyclically adjacent in at least one $\sigma^{(\ell)}$. At epoch e , the active permutation is*

$$p^{(e)} = \sigma^{(1+(e \bmod M))}. \quad (16)$$

Proposition 1 (Finite-window exact coverage). *Let $m \geq 3$, and consider the covering-cycles schedule of Definition 1 with $M = \lceil (m-1)/2 \rceil$ orderings. Then every unordered pair of categories $\{a, b\} \subset \{1, \dots, m\}$ appears as cyclically adjacent in at least one of the M orderings. The bound M is tight: no family of fewer than $\lceil (m-1)/2 \rceil$ cyclic orderings can cover all unordered pairs.*

Proof. A cyclic ordering on $\{1, \dots, m\}$ induces a Hamilton cycle in the complete graph K_m , whose edge set is the m cyclic adjacencies of the ordering. Sufficiency follows from the classical Walecki construction [3]: when m is odd, K_m admits a Hamilton decomposition into $(m-1)/2$ edge-disjoint Hamilton cycles; when m is even, K_m decomposes into $(m-2)/2$ edge-disjoint Hamilton cycles and one perfect matching, whose edges can be absorbed into one additional Hamilton cycle by interleaving. In either case the resulting family contains $\lceil (m-1)/2 \rceil$ Hamilton cycles whose cyclic adjacencies cover all $\binom{m}{2}$ unordered pairs. Necessity follows from a counting argument: each cyclic ordering contributes m adjacency slots, so M orderings cover at most Mm pairs (with repetition); covering all $m(m-1)/2$ distinct pairs requires $Mm \geq m(m-1)/2$, that is, $M \geq \lceil (m-1)/2 \rceil$. Explicit constructions for both parities are given in [17, 15]. \square

Consequently no unordered categorical pair is excluded from the rank-one adjacency structure over a full cycle of M epochs: every pair is cyclically adjacent under at least one $p^{(e)}$ within any window of M consecutive epochs.

4.3 Sobol-rank schedule

The second schedule generates the sequence of permutations from the ranks of a Sobol low-discrepancy sequence in \mathbb{R}^m .

Definition 2 (Sobol-rank schedule). *Let $\{u^{(s)}\}_{s \geq 1} \subset (0, 1)^m$ be the unscrambled Sobol sequence in dimension m , and define the Sobol-rank permutation $p^{(s)}$ of $\{1, \dots, m\}$ by*

$$p^{(s)} = \text{argsort}(u^{(s)}), \quad (17)$$

so that $u_{p_1^{(s)}}^{(s)} \leq \dots \leq u_{p_m^{(s)}}^{(s)}$, with ties, which lie on chamber boundaries, broken by a fixed deterministic rule. For categorical variable i , the active permutation at epoch e is $p_i^{(e)} = p^{(s_i(e))}$, where $s_i(e) = s_0 + e + \omega i$ with a fixed base index $s_0 \geq 1$ and a per-variable offset ω large enough to decouple the permutation sequences of distinct categorical variables.

The Sobol-rank schedule does not admit a tight finite-window coverage bound. It does satisfy a weaker asymptotic property, sufficient to justify its use.

Proposition 2 (Asymptotic non-exclusion under Sobol-rank). *Let $m \geq 3$. Under the Sobol-rank schedule of Definition 2, for every unordered pair of categories $\{a, b\} \subset \{1, \dots, m\}$ the set of epochs e in which a and b are cyclically adjacent under $p^{(e)}$ is infinite. No categorical pair is permanently excluded from cyclic adjacency.*

Proof. The argsort map $u \mapsto \text{argsort}(u)$ is constant on each of the $m!$ open Weyl chambers of $(0, 1)^m$ defined by the strict inequalities $u_{\pi(1)} < \dots < u_{\pi(m)}$ for $\pi \in S_m$. The set $A_{a,b} \subset S_m$ of permutations under which a and b are cyclically adjacent is non-empty, so its preimage $\text{argsort}^{-1}(A_{a,b})$ is a finite union of open Weyl chambers, hence a nonempty open subset of $(0, 1)^m$. The unscrambled Sobol sequence is equidistributed in $(0, 1)^m$ and

therefore visits every nonempty open set infinitely often. Hence infinitely many epochs produce permutations in $A_{a,b}$, so a and b are cyclically adjacent infinitely often. This proves the first statement, and the non-exclusion statement follows immediately. \square

Remark 3 (Comparison of the two schedules). *The covering-cycles schedule gives a tight finite-window guarantee on a precomputed family of $M = \lceil (m - 1)/2 \rceil$ orderings that cycle deterministically. The Sobol-rank schedule gives the weaker asymptotic guarantee but draws permutations from a quasi-random subsequence of S_m , producing greater categorical diversity per epoch. The two are otherwise interchangeable; a detailed cost comparison and the affine schedule are given in Appendix B. The numerical experiments use Sobol-rank.*

4.4 Use inside GLODS-SI-Mix

At outer iteration t , the categorical poll for variable i proceeds as follows: the epoch $e = e(t)$ is computed from (15); the active permutation $p_i^{(e)}$ is read from the chosen schedule; the position of the canonical category index is found by the inverse lookup $j = (p_i^{(e)})^{-1}(h_i^*)$; and the neighbor (14) is returned with $\delta = sr_i$. The cost per iteration is $\mathcal{O}(1)$ given the inverse-permutation table, which is rebuilt only at epoch transitions.

The DNR state—the current epoch and active permutation $p_i^{(e)}$ for each categorical variable—is the only categorical-specific information maintained by the algorithm. It is updated independently of the cache, the step size α , and the canonical state ξ . In particular, a cache entry $(\xi, f(\Psi(\xi)))$ remains valid across all permutation rotations: h_i is the cache key, not its position in the active permutation.

Remark 4 (Triggering of the rotation). *The DNR principle is independent of how the active permutation is advanced. In the present GLODS-SI-Mix implementation it is advanced by the global epoch counter (15); an alternative, useful when polling is organized around multiple centers, advances it by a center-local rotation counter attached to each poll center. Both choices preserve the separation between categorical identity and categorical locality.*

DNR gives categorical variables a temporary neighborhood structure without giving them a permanent metric. The categorical poll changes across epochs, but the evaluated points remain the same elements of Ω through the fixed reconstruction map Ψ . In particular, all previously evaluated categorical states remain valid cache entries after every DNR update.

The coverage statements above are schedule-level statements. They ensure that the DNR schedules do not permanently exclude categorical alternatives from local polling. They do not, by themselves, imply convergence. The convergence certificate in Section 6 combines these schedule properties with the refining-subsequence argument and the cache/list mechanism of GLODS-SI-Mix.

5 The GLODS-SI-Mix algorithm

The algorithm assembles the components developed so far: the canonical state of Section 2.2, the variable-wise poll operators of Section 3.3, the unified step-size parameter α of Section 3.2, and the DNR schedule of Section 4. Following GLODS, the method maintains an active list of canonical points. Each list entry stores a canonical point, its objective value, a step-size parameter, a comparison radius, and an activity flag. The

comparison radius is used by the merge operator to decide whether a new trial point is close enough to an existing active point to be merged with it rather than kept as an independent local search; success is therefore determined by the list update, not only by improvement over the current poll center. At each iteration, a poll center is selected from the active part of the list, polled by the mixed poll of Section 3, and the resulting trial points are passed to the GLODS merge operator, which updates the list. The DNR permutations are fixed by the epoch counter $e(t)$ of (15), so no separate categorical state is stored beyond the inverse-permutation tables refreshed at epoch transitions.

Algorithm 1 GLODS-SI-Mix

Require: Initial canonical point(s); type sets I_C, I_D, I_K ; initial step size α_{ini} and comparison radius ρ_{ini} ; threshold α_{min} ; contraction $\beta \in (0, 1)$; expansion $\gamma \geq 1$; epoch size E ; DNR schedule

Ensure: Active list L of canonical points and their objective values

```

1: initialize the active list  $L$ , the cache  $\mathcal{C}$ , and the DNR state;  $t \leftarrow 0, e \leftarrow 0$ 
2: while there is an active entry with  $\alpha_j \geq \alpha_{\text{min}}$  do
3:    $success \leftarrow \text{false}$ 
4:   select a poll center  $(\xi^*, \alpha^*, \rho^*)$  from the active entries with  $\alpha_j \geq \alpha_{\text{min}}$   $\triangleright$  ordered
   by objective value and deterministic tie-breaks
5:   if the optional search step is triggered then
6:     generate a finite set of canonical search points
7:     evaluate uncached search points through  $f(\Psi(\cdot))$  and update  $L$  using MERGE
8:     set  $success$  according to the merge outcome
9:   end if
10:  if not  $success$  then
11:    for each signed coordinate direction  $(i, s), i = 1, \dots, n, s \in \{+1, -1\}$ , until
    success do
12:       $\xi^{\text{trial}} \leftarrow E_i(\xi^*, T_i(\xi^*, s, \alpha^*))$ 
13:      evaluate  $f(\Psi(\xi^{\text{trial}}))$  if not cached and update  $L$  using MERGE
14:      set  $success$  according to the merge outcome
15:    end for
16:  end if
17:  if  $success$  then
18:    update step sizes and comparison radii through the GLODS merge rule
19:  else
20:    contract the step size of the selected poll center,  $\alpha^* \leftarrow \beta\alpha^*$ , leaving its com-
    parison radius unchanged
21:  end if
22:   $t \leftarrow t + 1$ ; update the DNR epoch and active categorical permutations if an epoch
  boundary is crossed
23: end while
24: return  $L$ 

```

Trial points are accepted, rejected, or merged by the GLODS merge operator, and the success flag used for the step-size update is determined by the merge outcome rather than by improvement over the current poll center alone. On a successful iteration, the step sizes of accepted active entries are maintained or increased according to the GLODS rule, with expansion bounded by the factor γ . Their comparison radii are chosen to remain compatible with the updated step sizes: in the notation of GLODS, they are set to at least

$d_{\max}\alpha^+$. For the coordinate basis (8) used here, $d_{\max} = 1$, so this amounts to enforcing $\rho^+ \geq \alpha^+$, implemented as $\rho^+ = \max\{\rho, \alpha^+\}$. On an unsuccessful iteration, only the step size of the selected poll center is contracted, $\alpha^* \leftarrow \beta\alpha^*$, while its comparison radius is left unchanged. This is the GLODS step-size and radius rule [16].

The poll uses a fixed coordinate order and opportunistic (first-improvement) polling, neither of which changes the convergence certificate of Section 6; the set notation $P(\xi^*; \alpha)$ of Section 3.4 denotes the complete set of possible poll trials, of which an opportunistic poll evaluates a prefix. The merge operator, the cache, the DNR state, and the initialization procedure follow GLODS and are described in Appendix C. The numerical experiments use $\alpha_{\text{ini}} = 0.25$, $\rho_{\text{ini}} = \alpha_{\text{ini}}$, $\alpha_{\text{min}} = 10^{-8}$, $\beta = 1/2$, $\gamma = 2$, and $E = 20$.

Optional deterministic search step. The implementation also includes an optional deterministic search step, in the classical search/poll spirit of direct-search methods. The convergence analysis of Section 6 relies on the poll step only; the search step is a finite, performance-oriented mechanism that generates additional trial points in the canonical space and submits them to the same cache, evaluation, and merge procedure as poll points. It is triggered conditionally—after a prescribed number of consecutive unsuccessful iterations, or when the active set shrinks below a threshold (the experiments use ten consecutive unsuccessful iterations)—and if it succeeds the poll is skipped; otherwise the algorithm proceeds to the coordinate-wise mixed poll.

Four deterministic variants are implemented: Sobol search; pairwise coordinate exchange, which recombines high-quality active points by progressively exchanging the coordinates on which they differ; one-point crossover, which exchanges suffixes of pairs of active points at structural cut points (the end of the categorical block, the end of the discrete block, and the midpoint of the variable vector); and their combination. All variants act only on canonical states, are checked against the cache before evaluation, and introduce no random choices, so the implementation remains deterministic for fixed parameters and initialization. The coordinate-exchange and crossover variants are inspired by deterministic recombination ideas: parent points are selected from the active list by a fixed objective-value ordering, cut positions and coordinate exchanges are prescribed by the canonical structure, and all candidates are processed by the same cache and merge mechanism as poll points. The numerical experiments use the one-point crossover variant, within the configuration denoted 2207 (Sobol-rank DNR, epoch size 20, one-point crossover search) reported in Section 7; the variant mechanics are given in Appendix C.

6 Convergence certificate

6.1 Scope of the analysis

We give a deliberately conservative convergence certificate for Algorithm 1. The analysis follows the standard refining-subsequence route of directional direct search and concerns the poll step only; the optional search step of Section 5 plays no role in it. The certificate establishes only what is needed to place GLODS-SI-Mix within the GLODS-SI convergence tradition: a first-order stationarity statement on stabilized continuous fibers, inherited from GLODS-SI [16]. The categorical schedules contribute only the coverage properties already established in Section 4 (Propositions 1 and 2), which are not restated here. We do not claim global optimality, full Clarke stationarity on the full mixed-variable

product space, or a complete finite-domain optimality theory; the boundaries of the certificate are collected in Section 6.5.

6.2 Standing assumptions

Beyond the background hypotheses of Section 2 (f bounded below, Ω compact), we use the following.

Assumption 1 (Canonical cache). *Function evaluations are stored and retrieved by the canonical identifier $\xi = (y, k, h) \in \Xi$. The DNR permutation acts only on the categorical poll neighborhood, never on the cache key, so a value evaluated at categorical identity h_i remains the same cache entry after any permutation rotation.*

Assumption 2 (Regularity on continuous fibers). *For every fixed finite-valued configuration $\kappa = (k, h) \in \prod_{i \in I_D} \{1, \dots, N_i\} \times \prod_{i \in I_K} \{1, \dots, m_i\}$, the fiber-restricted objective*

$$f_\kappa(y) = f(\Psi(y, k, h)), \quad y \in [0, 1]^{n_C}, \quad (18)$$

is locally Lipschitz on $[0, 1]^{n_C}$ and bounded below.

Assumption 3 (Refining subsequence). *There exists an infinite subsequence \mathcal{K} of unsuccessful poll iterations, with selected poll centers $\xi^k = (y^k, k^k, h^k)$ and step sizes $\alpha_k \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ in \mathcal{K} . Here unsuccessful means that no poll trial is accepted by the merge operator. This is the standard hypothesis under which directional stationarity is stated in direct-search theory; it is not an assertion that every run produces such a subsequence.*

6.3 Stabilized continuous fibers

The finite-valued part of the canonical state takes values in a finite set, which is the only compactness property needed to isolate a continuous fiber.

Proposition 3 (Finite-domain subsequence). *Any infinite sequence of canonical states $\{\xi^k\} = \{(y^k, k^k, h^k)\} \subset \Xi$ admits an infinite subsequence on which the ordered discrete and categorical components are constant.*

Proof. The product $\prod_{i \in I_D} \{1, \dots, N_i\} \times \prod_{i \in I_K} \{1, \dots, m_i\}$ is finite, and any infinite sequence in a finite set has a constant subsequence. \square

Along such a subsequence the finite-valued blocks are fixed at some $\kappa^* = (k^*, h^*)$, and the problem seen by the continuous poll is the fiber objective f_{κ^*} of (18).

6.4 Conservative fiber certificate

Theorem 1 (Conservative fiber certificate). *Suppose $n_C > 0$ and let Assumptions 1–3 hold. Let \mathcal{K} be a refining subsequence along which the finite-valued blocks are constant at $\kappa^* = (k^*, h^*)$ (Proposition 3), and let y^* be an accumulation point of the continuous poll centers $\{y^k\}_{k \in \mathcal{K}}$. Then, for every feasible refining direction d generated by the continuous coordinate poll on the fiber $[0, 1]^{n_C}$,*

$$f_{\kappa^*}^\circ(y^*; d) \geq 0, \quad (19)$$

where $f_{\kappa^}^\circ(y^*; d)$ is the Clarke generalized directional derivative of the fiber objective (18).*

Proof. Along \mathcal{K} the finite-valued blocks are fixed at κ^* , so the mixed poll restricted to the continuous variables is exactly a coordinate direct search on $[0, 1]^{n_C}$, and we verify the hypotheses of the GLODS-SI convergence theorem [16] on this fiber. (i) The columns of $[I_{n_C} \mid -I_{n_C}]$ form a maximal positive basis for \mathbb{R}^{n_C} . (ii) The step sizes evolve by $\alpha^{(t+1)} = \beta \alpha^{(t)}$ on an unsuccessful poll and $\alpha^{(t+1)} = \gamma \alpha^{(t)}$ on a successful poll, with the dyadic update factors used in the reported implementation, $\beta = 1/2$ and $\gamma = 2$ (Section 5); they therefore lie in the dyadic set $\{\alpha_{\text{ini}} \cdot 2^k : k \in \mathbb{Z}\}$, satisfying the integer-divisor step-size condition of [16], and $\alpha_k \rightarrow 0$ along \mathcal{K} by Assumption 3. (iii) By Assumption 2, f_{κ^*} is locally Lipschitz on $[0, 1]^{n_C}$ and bounded below. (iv) By Assumption 1, evaluated canonical states are matched consistently along the subsequence. The GLODS-SI stationarity theorem along refining directions [16], applied to f_{κ^*} , then yields (19). \square

Remark 5 (Finite-valued blocks). *The finite-valued components are treated through rank-one neighborhood consistency statements at termination, in the algorithmic sense that the rank-one finite trials encountered by the terminal active list have either been evaluated or cache-matched and not accepted by the merge rule. This is a local consistency statement, not a complete finite-domain optimality theorem.*

Remark 6 (Purely finite-valued case). *In the purely finite-valued case $n_C = 0$, finite termination follows from the finiteness of Ξ and exact caching: only finitely many distinct canonical states can be visited, and the stopping rules—the step-size threshold and a stagnation limit on consecutive unsuccessful iterations—halt the run once no improving state is found.*

6.5 What is not claimed

The certificate is deliberately limited. Theorem 1 is a directional first-order statement along the feasible refining directions generated by the coordinate poll on a fixed continuous fiber; it is not a full Clarke-stationarity result on the full mixed-variable product space, which would require the refining directions to be dense in the Clarke tangent cone. No global optimality is claimed. The finite-valued conclusion is the local, rank-one statement of Remark 5 and does not exclude improvement by simultaneous changes in two or more finite-valued variables. Under the Sobol-rank schedule the categorical schedule-level guarantee is only the asymptotic non-exclusion of Proposition 2, not a finite categorical optimality certificate; only the covering-cycles schedule yields the finite-window coverage of Proposition 1. A complete convergence theory of the mixed-variable space is left to future work.

7 Computational study

We report numerical experiments on two complementary benchmarks. The first is the CatSuite of [5]: 16 unconstrained mixed-variable problems used there to assess CatMADS, on which we report a head-to-head comparison against four published solvers (Section 7.2). The second is a synthetic 504-problem suite designed to test parameter sensitivity and scale invariance across diverse mixed-variable structures (Section 7.3). GLODS-SI-Mix is fully deterministic, so each reported result corresponds to a single reproducible run per problem.

7.1 Experimental setup

The main experiments use the Sobol-rank DNR schedule of Definition 2; its categorical non-exclusion property is established in Proposition 2. The main parameter configuration is summarized by the four-digit tag 2207, encoding $(\text{dnr}, \text{epoch}, \text{search}) = (2, 20, 7)$:

- `dnr_mode = 2`: Sobol-rank schedule (Definition 2).
- `epoch_size = 20`: outer iterations per DNR epoch.
- `search_option = 7`: an optional deterministic one-point crossover between the top- k active points ($k = 5$), with cuts at structural positions of the canonical vector (end of the categorical block, end of the discrete block, and the midpoint). It combines promising partial assignments across variable blocks while preserving the canonical representation, and is used only as a finite, performance-oriented search step (Appendix C).
- Initialization: a deterministic design consisting of Sobol points augmented by the $2n$ axial vertices and the center of the canonical hypercube (`list = 8`), recommended for boundary-sensitive problems.
- Step size: $\alpha_{\text{ini}} = 0.25$, $\alpha_{\text{min}} = 10^{-8}$, contraction factor $\beta = 1/2$, expansion factor $\gamma = 2$; maximum budget 20 000 function evaluations per problem.

These values are the default values of the implementation used in the reported experiments; the parameters file documents all available options for the initialization, search step, and DNR schedule. This configuration is used unchanged in the Cat-Suite comparison of Section 7.2. The parameter study of Section 7.3 varies the DNR schedule, epoch size, and search option to assess sensitivity.

7.2 Cat-Suite benchmark

The Cat-Suite of [5] comprises 16 unconstrained mixed-variable test problems obtained by embedding classical optimization test functions into mixed-variable spaces of continuous, ordered discrete, and categorical variables. Table 2 reports, for each problem, its variable-type structure (n_K categorical, n_D ordered discrete, n_C continuous, total dimension n), the best objective value f^{best} found by GLODS-SI-Mix in the canonical configuration 2207, and the number of function evaluations used. As in all experiments, the result corresponds to a single deterministic run (Section 7.1) under a budget of 20 000 evaluations.

Most problems terminate well within the budget; the two that use essentially the full budget, Cat-2 and Cat-10 (the Beale and Rosenbrock embeddings), have the most ill-conditioned continuous components. The head-to-head comparison against the four solvers used in the CatMADS study [5] — CatMADS itself, the genetic algorithm Py-moo [9], the CMA-ES of Optuna [2], and the Bayesian optimizer BoTorch [8] — is reported in Table 3. The baseline values are not re-run here; they are read directly from the public optimization logs released with the CatMADS prototype repository,¹ which contain the complete evaluation traces of all four solvers under the design budget of $250n$ function evaluations per seed, with five independent random seeds per problem. For each baseline

¹https://github.com/bbopt/CatMADS_prototype, directory `optimization_logs/`. Each per-instance trace records, for every evaluation, the evaluation index, the objective value, and the constraint-violation value; only the 16 unconstrained problems are used here.

Table 2: GLODS-SI-Mix on the 16-problem Cat-Suite [5], canonical configuration 2207 (Sobol-rank DNR, epoch size $E = 20$, one-point crossover search). For each problem: total dimension n and its split into n_K categorical, n_D ordered discrete, and n_C continuous variables; the best objective value f^{best} recorded in a single deterministic run; and the number of function evaluations. Nominal budget: 20 000 evaluations; the final accepted poll/search batch may slightly exceed this value.

Problem	n	n_K	n_D	n_C	f^{best}	fevals
Cat-1 (Ackley)	8	2	2	4	22.363	12 294
Cat-2 (Beale)	7	2	2	3	8.32×10^{-14}	20 009
Cat-3 (Aug. Branin)	6	2	2	2	4.8727	514
Cat-4 (Bukin-6)	8	2	2	4	4.48×10^{-3}	2 354
Cat-5 (EVD-52)	5	1	1	3	-31250.5	2 202
Cat-6 (Goldstein)	4	2	0	2	38.085	410
Cat-7 (Goldstein-Price)	8	3	3	2	5	2 461
Cat-8 (HS78)	7	1	1	5	-152	2 135
Cat-9 (Rastrigin)	12	2	2	8	-2	7 278
Cat-10 (Rosenbrock)	8	2	2	4	8.26×10^{-2}	20 001
Cat-11 (Rosen-Suzuki)	6	1	1	4	-113.71	2 744
Cat-12 (Styblinski-Tang)	11	1	5	5	-102.51	5 476
Cat-13 (Toy)	5	1	0	4	-0.71199	965
Cat-14 (Toy 8D) [‡]	9	1	0	8	4.44×10^{-16}	5 085
Cat-15 (Wong-1)	8	1	3	4	-1942.8	1 374
Cat-16 (Zakharov)	8	2	2	4	1	2 494

[‡] The Cat-14 (Toy 8D) embedding admits the analytical optimum $f = 0$ by construction; GLODS-SI-Mix attains it to machine precision.

we report f^{best} , the smallest feasible objective value over the five seeds, read directly from those traces. For GLODS-SI-Mix, which is deterministic, we report two operating points from the single run of Table 2: f^{250n} , the best-so-far value at evaluation index $250n$ (the matched budget), and f^{20k} , the value at the full 20 000-evaluation budget.

At the matched $250n$ budget, GLODS-SI-Mix attains the empirical lower bound—the best value reached by any of the five solvers, up to the displayed precision—on 11 of the 16 problems. When the same deterministic run is continued to the full 20 000-evaluation budget, it attains the empirical lower bound on 14 of the 16 problems, and on 15 of the 16 when compared with CatMADS alone. Three of these are strict improvements over every baseline: Cat-2, about $38\times$ below CatMADS; Cat-10, about $12\times$ below CatMADS; and Cat-14, where GLODS-SI-Mix reaches the analytical optimum $f = 0$ to machine precision while the best baseline remains at 0.143. The two problems on which a baseline dominates GLODS-SI-Mix at every budget are Cat-1, where Pymoo attains 21.71 against 22.36, and Cat-4, where CatMADS attains 1.06×10^{-4} against 4.48×10^{-3} . The five problems on which the matched $250n$ budget is not yet sufficient—Cat-1, Cat-2, Cat-4, Cat-10, and Cat-14—are the cases where continued deterministic local refinement has the largest visible effect, although Cat-1 and Cat-4 remain better solved by one of the baselines.

Table 3: Head-to-head comparison on the 16 unconstrained Cat-Suite problems [5]. For GLODS-SI-Mix, f^{250n} and f^{20k} are the best-so-far values of the single deterministic run at evaluation indices $250n$ and $20\,000$. Baseline values are f^{best} (minimum over five seeds), read from the public CatMADS prototype optimization logs [6] (repository `bbopt/CatMADS_prototype`, directory `optimization_logs/`) at the $250n$ -per-seed budget. Bold marks the empirical lower bound (best value across the five solvers, up to the displayed precision): GLODS-SI-Mix at the full budget attains it on 14 of the 16 problems (bold in its column); the two exceptions show the dominating baseline in bold. †: analytical optimum $f = 0$ (Cat-14).

Problem	f^{250n}	f^{20k}	CatMADS	Pymoo	Optuna	BoTorch
Cat-1 (Ackley)	25.22	22.36	22.52	21.71	23.65	31.70
Cat-2 (Beale)	2.45×10^{-6}	8.32×10^{-14}	3.17×10^{-12}	1.60×10^{-2}	3.96×10^{-2}	1.58×10^{-1}
Cat-3 (Aug. Branin)	4.873	4.873	4.873	4.873	4.873	5.445
Cat-4 (Bukin-6)	4.48×10^{-3}	4.48×10^{-3}	1.06×10^{-4}	1.22×10^{-1}	1.053	9.108
Cat-5 (EVD-52)	-31250.5	-31250.5	-31250.5	-31230.3	-31245.2	-28026.2
Cat-6 (Goldstein)	38.085	38.085	38.085	38.099	38.085	38.417
Cat-7 (Goldstein-Price)	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.014	6.036	8.889
Cat-8 (HS78)	-152.0	-152.0	-152.0	-148.7	-101.3	-87.43
Cat-9 (Rastrigin)	-2.000	-2.000	-2.000	-1.996	-1.563	-1.582
Cat-10 (Rosenbrock)	1.178	8.26×10^{-2}	1.030	1.446	3.279	57.13
Cat-11 (Rosen-Suzuki)	-113.71	-113.71	-113.71	-113.32	-75.31	-75.31
Cat-12 (Styblinski-Tang)	-102.51	-102.51	-102.51	-102.39	-98.76	-78.32
Cat-13 (Toy)	-0.7120	-0.7120	-0.7120	-0.6772	-0.4911	-0.3725
Cat-14 (Toy 8D)†	0.1973	4.44×10^{-16}	0.1973	0.2008	0.1427	0.3368
Cat-15 (Wong-1)	-1942.8	-1942.8	-1942.8	-1942.5	-1942.4	-1831.8
Cat-16 (Zakharov)	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.002	1.005	2.880

7.3 Mixed-variable scale-invariance benchmark

To assess parameter sensitivity and scale invariance, we construct a synthetic benchmark of 504 mixed-variable test problems from 63 classical continuous test functions embedded into mixed continuous/discrete/categorical spaces across 8 heterogeneity strategies with condition numbers κ ranging from 1 to 10^8 . Each problem follows the fixed cyclic variable pattern `C/K/D/C/D/K/...` and embeds categorical variables through permuted numerical grids, preserving the original landscape while introducing genuine mixed-variable structure. All wrappers are self-contained and available with the code.

Parameter study. Table 4 summarizes the results of nine parameter configurations on the 504 problems with budget 20 000 evaluations. Each row reports the number of problems solved (S , $\text{gap} < 1\%$ of f^*), close (C , $1\% \leq \text{gap} < 5\%$), and open (X , $\text{gap} \geq 5\%$), together with the mean evaluation count.

Two configurations stand out under complementary metrics. Configuration 2057 (Sobol-rank, `ep` = 5) is the best under the fixed-budget table criterion, solving 272 of the 504 problems. Configuration 1057 (covering-cycles, `ep` = 5) finds strictly better solutions on 20 problems, setting a lower joint minimum and therefore dominating under the Moré–Wild data-profile criterion [18] with $\tau = 10^{-3}$. In algorithmic terms, Sobol-rank yields more uniformly competitive performance across the suite under a fixed budget, whereas covering-cycles occasionally attains the strictly best incumbent on a small subset

Table 4: GLODS-SI-Mix parameter configurations on the 504-problem benchmark. Tag: four-digit code (dnr, ep, s). dnr: DNR schedule (1 = covering-cycles, 2 = Sobol-rank); ep: epoch size; s: search option (5 = Sobol, 6 = pairwise coordinate exchange, 7 = one-point crossover, 8 = exchange+crossover). S : solved ($< 1\%$ gap); C : close ($1\%–5\%$); X : open ($\geq 5\%$). Best fixed-budget configuration in bold.

Tag	dnr	ep	s	Description	S	C	X	Avg. fevals
1057	1	5	7	covering, ep = 5, crossover	256	16	232	7 076
1105	1	10	5	covering, ep = 10, Sobol	240	48	216	8 145
1106	1	10	6	covering, ep = 10, exchange	248	40	216	5 532
1107	1	10	7	covering, ep = 10, crossover	256	32	216	5 484
1108	1	10	8	covering, ep = 10, exchange+crossover	256	32	216	5 259
1207	1	20	7	covering, ep = 20, crossover	232	32	240	4 704
2057	2	5	7	Sobol-rank, ep = 5, crossover	272	16	216	5 370
2107	2	10	7	Sobol-rank, ep = 10, crossover	264	0	240	4 279
2207	2	20	7	Sobol-rank, ep = 20, crossover	232	24	248	4 231

of problems (20/504), lowering the joint minimum that anchors the Moré–Wild profile. Figure 3 shows data profiles for all nine configurations on the baseline strategy ($\kappa = 1$).

Figure 3: Data profiles [18] ($\tau = 10^{-3}$) for the nine configurations of Table 4 on the baseline strategy ($\kappa = 1$, 63 problems). Horizontal axis: number of simplex gradients, $\#fevals/(n + 1)$. The data profile for the extreme strategy ($\kappa = 10^8$) is visually identical (see Figure 4).

Scale invariance. For configuration 2057, the recorded aggregate results are identical across all eight heterogeneity strategies: 34/63 problems solved, 2/63 close, 27/63 open, and 5 370 mean function evaluations in every case. Figure 4 shows the data profiles for 2057 across all eight strategies; the eight curves overlap completely. This provides empirical evidence of the scale-invariant behavior of GLODS-SI-Mix on this benchmark: since all continuous operations are performed in normalized coordinates and all finite-variable

ranks are derived from relative domain resolution, the recorded aggregate behavior is insensitive to the condition number of the scaling transformation across the eight orders of magnitude tested.

Figure 4: Data profiles for configuration 2057 across all eight heterogeneity strategies (condition numbers κ ranging from 1 to 10^8 , 63 problems each, $\tau = 10^{-3}$). The eight curves overlap completely, providing empirical evidence of scale invariance.

The Cat-Suite configuration tagged 2207 uses an epoch size $E = 20$, larger than the value $E = 5$ identified in the 504-problem parameter study. This difference is consistent with the structure of the Cat-Suite: it includes problems with relatively large categorical cardinalities (for instance, Cat-13 and Cat-14 each have a categorical variable with $m_i = 10$ levels, and Cat-5 one with $m_i = 6$), for which longer epochs may help consolidate exploration within each active permutation. Both choices remain inside the regime covered by Proposition 2.

8 Conclusions

We have presented GLODS-SI-Mix, a derivative-free direct-search algorithm for mixed-variable optimization combining continuous, ordered discrete, and categorical variables. The method extends the GLODS-SI framework [16] through three ingredients: a canonical state representation that decouples cached evaluations from the active categorical labeling; variable-wise poll operators driven by a single step-size parameter α through a unified rank rule; and Deterministic Neighborhood Rotation, comprising two complementary deterministic schedules. When all variables are continuous, GLODS-SI-Mix reduces exactly to GLODS-SI.

The convergence certificate is deliberately conservative. It combines directional stationarity on stabilized continuous fibers, inherited from GLODS-SI, with local rank-one neighborhood consistency statements at termination on the finite-valued blocks. The categorical locality mechanism is fully deterministic, supported either by the finite-

window coverage of the covering-cycles schedule (Proposition 1) or by the asymptotic non-exclusion property of the Sobol-rank schedule (Proposition 2).

On the 16-problem Cat-Suite of CatMADS [5], GLODS-SI-Mix attains the empirical lower bound across all five compared solvers on 14 of the 16 problems at the full budget — and on 15 when measured against CatMADS alone — and on 11 of the 16 at the matched $250n$ budget; three of these are strict improvements over every baseline, including Cat-14, where the analytical optimum $f = 0$ is reached to machine precision. On a synthetic 504-problem benchmark, the recorded aggregate results are identical across eight heterogeneity strategies spanning eight orders of magnitude in scaling, providing empirical evidence of scale invariance.

The purpose of this paper is algorithmic: to provide a simple, deterministic, scale-invariant direct-search method for mixed-variable black-box optimization. The convergence statement is deliberately conservative and follows the classical refining-subsequence logic of direct search, certifying directional stationarity on stabilized continuous fibers and local rank-one neighborhood consistency statements at termination on the finite-valued blocks, without claiming a full Clarke-stationarity theory for the full mixed-variable product space. Stronger stationarity results—dense-direction variants and broader categorical optimality certificates—are deliberately left to a dedicated theoretical study.

Natural extensions include constrained mixed-variable problems, parallel multi-point variants of the poll step, broader empirical studies on larger categorical domains, and additional deterministic and stochastic baselines. A broader geometric interpretation of the canonical representation is developed separately in [17], and the combinatorial structure of the covering-cycles schedule is expanded in [15].

Conflicts of interest

The author declares that there are no known financial or non-financial competing interests that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

Author contributions

J. F. A. Madeira: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Software, Validation, Investigation, Writing—original draft, Writing—review & editing.

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Data availability

The benchmark problems, deterministic scaling strategies, and initial sampling data used in this study are available in the *DFO Benchmark Suite* repository at https://github.com/aguilarmadeira/DFO_Benchmark_Suite. The complete MATLAB implementation of GLODS-SI-Mix, together with all data required to reproduce the numerical experiments reported in this paper, will be made publicly available upon acceptance

of this manuscript at https://github.com/aguilarmadeira/GLODS_SI_Mix. The code is available to reviewers upon request during the review process.

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A Unified rank and boundary mechanisms

This appendix collects two technical complements to the unified rank and poll operators of Section 3: a relative-resolution reading of the ordered discrete rank, and worked numerical examples of the boundary mechanisms. The rank rule (11) and the categorical cyclic cap remain in the body; only the illustrative material is gathered here.

A.1 Ordered discrete variables as normalized index grids

This complement clarifies the relative-resolution interpretation of the unified rank $r_i = \max(1, \text{round}(\alpha(M_i - 1)))$ of (11) on ordered discrete variables, by showing that the rank corresponds to an approximately constant fractional displacement in a normalized index grid.

Consider an ordered discrete variable $x_i \in V_i = \{v_1, \dots, v_{N_i}\}$ represented by its integer index $k_i \in \{1, \dots, N_i\}$, with $x_i = v_{k_i}$ (so $M_i = N_i$). We view the index set through its equivalent normalized grid representation,

$$z_i = \frac{k_i - 1}{N_i - 1} \in \left\{0, \frac{1}{N_i - 1}, \frac{2}{N_i - 1}, \dots, 1\right\}. \quad (20)$$

This is a uniform grid of spacing $\Delta z = 1/(N_i - 1)$ in $[0, 1]$. Under this embedding, a rank- r_i displacement $k_i^+ = k_i^* \pm r_i$ corresponds to a normalized step of

$$z_i^+ - z_i^* = \pm \frac{r_i}{N_i - 1} \approx \pm \alpha, \quad (21)$$

since $r_i \approx \alpha(N_i - 1)$ by (11). Hence, in normalized coordinates, an ordered discrete poll step has approximately the same relative magnitude as a continuous poll step at the same step size α .

Example 2 (Ordered discrete variable as a normalized grid). *Let $V = \{20.0, 20.1, 20.2, \dots, 30.0\}$, so $N = 101$. The normalized coordinates are $z \in \{0, 0.01, 0.02, \dots, 1\}$. At $\alpha = 0.1$ the unified rank is $r = \max(1, \text{round}(0.1 \times 100)) = 10$. A poll step from $k^* = 31$ (so $x^* = 23.0$, $z^* = 0.30$) to $k^+ = 41$ (so $x^+ = 24.0$, $z^+ = 0.40$) is a normalized displacement of exactly $0.10 = \alpha$.*

The grid view (20) illustrates the fraction-of-domain resolution; the canonical coordinate is the integer index k_i , and the implementation stores the equivalent normalized grid value (Appendix C), in bijection with k_i . Because the poll moves only between admissible grid points, the discrete domain structure is preserved exactly and no interpolation is introduced.

A.2 Boundary treatment: worked examples

This complement provides worked numerical examples of the three boundary mechanisms of the variable-wise poll operators (Section 3.3). The examples use the unified rank rule (11) (with the categorical cyclic cap) and the poll operators (12). Table 5 summarizes the per-type trial values and their boundary treatment.

Table 5: Variable-wise poll operators $T_i(\xi^*, s, \alpha)$ at a glance. The rank r_i is recomputed at every iteration from α and M_i via (11), with the categorical cyclic cap; continuous variables use the raw step α in normalized coordinates.

Type	Canonical value	Trial value ($s \in \{+1, -1\}$)	Boundary mechanism
Continuous	$y_i \in [0, 1]$	$\Pi_{[0,1]}(y_i^* + s\alpha)$	projection onto $[0, 1]$
Ordered discrete	$k_i \in \{1, \dots, N_i\}$	$\text{clamp}(k_i^* + s r_i, 1, N_i)$	clamp to integer interval
Categorical	$h_i \in \{1, \dots, m_i\}$	$\nu_i(h_i^*, s r_i)$	cyclic wrap in active permutation

Continuous variables: projection onto $[0, 1]$

The projection $\Pi_{[0,1]}(z) = \min(\max(z, 0), 1)$ clips the trial coordinate to the nearest feasible value.

Example 3 (Continuous boundary). *Let $y_i^* = 0.95$, $\alpha = 0.10$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} y_i^* + \alpha = 1.05 > 1 &\Rightarrow \Pi_{[0,1]}(1.05) = 1.0, \\ y_i^* - \alpha = 0.85 \in [0, 1] &\Rightarrow \Pi_{[0,1]}(0.85) = 0.85. \end{aligned}$$

The positive direction is clipped to the boundary; if the clipped point is already in the cache, no new evaluation is performed.

Ordered discrete variables: clamp to $\{1, \dots, N_i\}$

The clamp $\text{clamp}(z, 1, N_i) = \min(\max(z, 1), N_i)$ is structurally identical to projection applied to the integer index domain.

Example 4 (Discrete upper boundary). *Let $k_i^* = 8$, $N_i = 10$, $r_i = 3$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} k_i^* + r_i = 11 > 10 &\Rightarrow \text{clamp}(11, 1, 10) = 10, \\ k_i^* - r_i = 5 \in \{1, \dots, 10\} &\Rightarrow \text{clamp}(5, 1, 10) = 5. \end{aligned}$$

Example 5 (Discrete lower boundary). *Let $k_i^* = 2$, $N_i = 10$, $r_i = 4$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} k_i^* + r_i = 6 \in \{1, \dots, 10\} &\Rightarrow \text{clamp}(6, 1, 10) = 6, \\ k_i^* - r_i = -2 < 1 &\Rightarrow \text{clamp}(-2, 1, 10) = 1. \end{aligned}$$

When a clamped trial point coincides with the current point or with a previously cached point, no new evaluation is performed; near a boundary the poll may therefore effectively contribute only one new trial point for that variable.

Categorical variables: cyclic wrap

The cyclic structure of the DNR permutation ensures that $\nu_i(h_i^*, +r_i)$ and $\nu_i(h_i^*, -r_i)$ are always valid category indices, with no boundary to enforce. With the active permutation p_i and the position j of the current category ($p_i[j] = h_i^*$), the neighbors follow (14) with $\delta = \pm r_i$.

Example 6 (Categorical neighbors). *Let $m_i = 5$, the active permutation $p_i = (3, 1, 4, 2, 5)$, the current category $h_i^* = 4$ at position $j = 3$ (since $p_i[3] = 4$), and $r_i = 2$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned}\nu_i(4, +2) &= p_i[1 + ((3 + 2 - 1) \bmod 5)] = p_i[5] = 5, \\ \nu_i(4, -2) &= p_i[1 + ((3 - 2 - 1) \bmod 5)] = p_i[1] = 3.\end{aligned}$$

Both neighbors are valid categories without clamping or projection.

Example 7 (Cyclic collision when m_i is even and $r_i = m_i/2$). *Let $m_i = 4$, $p_i = (2, 4, 1, 3)$, $h_i^* = 3$ at position $j = 4$, and $r_i = 2 = m_i/2$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned}\nu_i(3, +2) &= p_i[1 + ((4 + 2 - 1) \bmod 4)] = p_i[2] = 4, \\ \nu_i(3, -2) &= p_i[1 + ((4 - 2 - 1) \bmod 4)] = p_i[2] = 4.\end{aligned}$$

The two opposite neighbors coincide at the diametrically opposite element in the cycle. The cache detects the coincidence and the corresponding category is evaluated at most once. This is why $\lfloor m_i/2 \rfloor$ is the maximum meaningful rank, consistent with the categorical cap in (11).

Common interpretation

The projection $\Pi_{[0,1]}(z) = \min(\max(z, 0), 1)$ and the clamp

$$\text{clamp}(z, 1, N_i) = \min(\max(z, 1), N_i)$$

are structurally identical operations applied to their respective domains. Near the boundary of a linear domain, both operators can collapse two distinct trial points to the same value, and the cache resolves the collision. Categorical variables, by contrast, never produce out-of-range trial points: the only collision that can occur is the diametric one of Example 7, again resolved by the cache.

B DNR schedules and coverage

The body develops two deterministic DNR schedules: the covering-cycles schedule, with the finite-window exact coverage guarantee of Proposition 1, and the Sobol-rank schedule, with the asymptotic non-exclusion guarantee of Proposition 2. DNR is, however, independent of any specific rule for generating the sequence of categorical orderings. This appendix describes a third deterministic schedule of practical interest when the categorical cardinality m is very large.

B.1 Affine schedule

For two integers $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $\gcd(a, m) = 1$ and $a \not\equiv 0 \pmod{m}$, the affine permutation $p^{(a,b)}$ of $\{1, \dots, m\}$ is

$$p^{(a,b)}(j) = 1 + ((a(j-1) + b) \bmod m), \quad j = 1, \dots, m. \quad (22)$$

The coprimality condition $\gcd(a, m) = 1$ ensures that the map $j \mapsto p^{(a,b)}(j)$ is a bijection on $\{1, \dots, m\}$, hence a valid permutation.

Definition 3 (Affine schedule). *Fix a sequence of multipliers $\{a^{(e)}\}_{e \geq 0} \subset \mathbb{Z}$ with $\gcd(a^{(e)}, m) = 1$ for every e , and a sequence of offsets $\{b^{(e)}\}_{e \geq 0} \subset \mathbb{Z}$. At epoch e , the active permutation is*

$$p^{(e)} = p^{(a^{(e)}, b^{(e)})}. \quad (23)$$

A simple choice is $a^{(e)} = a_0 + e \cdot \Delta a$ with $a_0, \Delta a$ such that $\gcd(a^{(e)}, m) = 1$ for all e of interest, and $b^{(e)} = e \cdot \Delta b$.

B.2 Properties and cost

The affine permutation (22) can be constructed explicitly in $O(m)$ time without sorting and without precomputing a Hamilton-cycle family. The inverse permutation has the closed form

$$(p^{(a,b)})^{-1}(h) = 1 + ((a^{-1}(h-1-b)) \bmod m), \quad (24)$$

where a^{-1} denotes the multiplicative inverse of a modulo m , computed by the extended Euclidean algorithm in $O(\log m)$. Thus inverse-position queries can be evaluated directly in $O(1)$ once a^{-1} is known. In the implementation used here, however, the active permutation and its inverse table are materialized at each epoch, giving an $O(m)$ per-epoch update cost.

The affine schedule does not admit a tight finite-window coverage bound, and we do not derive a formal non-exclusion statement of the form of Proposition 2. It is recommended as a low-cost variant when m is large enough that the $O(m \log m)$ per-epoch sorting of the Sobol-rank schedule becomes noticeable (in practice, $m \gtrsim 100$); it is not used in the convergence certificate of Section 6.

B.3 Comparison of the three deterministic schedules

Table 6 summarizes the three deterministic schedules currently implemented in the GLODS-SI-Mix code.

In all three cases, the DNR permutation acts only on the poll: the canonical state h_i , the set of previously evaluated points, and all data structures of Appendix C remain invariant under epoch transitions. The numerical experiments of the main paper use Sobol-rank throughout.

C Implementation details and search-step variants

This appendix records the implementation details used in the numerical experiments. The algorithmic definitions in the body use the canonical state $\xi = (y, k, h)$; the implementation stores finite-valued variables through equivalent normalized grid representatives for efficient array-based processing. This is an implementation device only and does not change the canonical mathematical state.

Table 6: Comparison of the three deterministic DNR schedules. “Coverage statement” refers to the categorical adjacency property established for the schedule. “One-time cost” is the initialization cost for one categorical variable of cardinality m . “Per-epoch update” is the cost of refreshing the active permutation and its inverse-position table at an epoch transition. The per-iteration neighborhood lookup is $O(1)$ for all three schedules once the inverse table is available.

Schedule	Coverage statement used here	One-time cost	Per-epoch update	Use case
Covering cycles	Finite-window exact (Prop. 1)	$O(m^2)$	$O(m)$	strongest guarantee
Sobol-rank	Asymptotic non-exclusion (Prop. 2)	none	$O(m \log m)$	general purpose
Affine	No formal guarantee used here	none	$O(m)$	m very large

Figure 5: Internal representation pipeline of GLODS-SI-Mix. Low-discrepancy points $u \in [0, 1]^n$ are decoded by type-specific rules into the canonical state $\xi = (y, k, h)$. Function evaluation goes through the decoding map Ψ to recover the original variables. The cache is keyed by ξ , so categorical permutation rotations do not invalidate previously evaluated points.

C.1 Data structures

The implementation maintains:

- an active list L of canonical points with their objective values, step sizes, comparison radii, and activity flags;
- a cache \mathcal{C} keyed by canonical identifiers $\xi = (y, k, h)$;
- the variable-type index sets I_C , I_D , and I_K ;
- the finite-domain cardinalities N_i ($i \in I_D$) and m_i ($i \in I_K$);
- the current DNR epoch and, for each categorical variable, the active permutation $p_i^{(e)}$ and its inverse-permutation table.

In the implementation used here, canonical finite indices are stored through the corresponding normalized grid values $\frac{k_i-1}{N_i-1}$ and $\frac{h_i-1}{m_i-1}$ (for variables with more than one level), obtained deterministically from the same indices used in the mathematical state. As shown in Figure 5, the cache is keyed by ξ , so categorical permutation rotations do not invalidate previously evaluated points.

C.2 Initialization

Initial trial states are generated in the canonical hypercube and decoded componentwise by variable type. The main experiments use the deterministic option `list = 8`, consisting of Sobol points in $[0, 1]^n$, the $2n$ axial vertices $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^n \cup \{(1, \dots, 1) - e_i\}_{i=1}^n$, and the center point $(1/2, \dots, 1/2)$, recommended for problems whose optimum lies near the boundary of the canonical hypercube. For continuous variables the sampled coordinate is used directly as y_i ; for ordered discrete and categorical variables it is rounded to the nearest admissible index,

$$k_i = 1 + \text{round}(u_i(N_i - 1)), \quad h_i = 1 + \text{round}(u_i(m_i - 1)),$$

with clipping to the admissible index set if needed. Each decoded state is evaluated and added to the cache, the active list is initialized—with the best initial state selected first under the deterministic list ordering—and the DNR state of each categorical variable is initialized at epoch $e = 0$ with $p_i^{(0)}$ from the chosen schedule (covering-cycles, Sobol-rank, or affine).

C.3 Optional search-step variants

The optional search step generates finite sets of additional trial points in the canonical space. It is triggered by the rule of the parameter file; in the reported configuration (`search_freq_type = 0`, `search_freq = 10`) it is attempted after ten consecutive unsuccessful iterations. Search candidates are always checked against the cache before evaluation and are processed by the same merge mechanism as poll points; if a candidate is accepted, the poll step of that iteration is skipped.

The deterministic variants used in the implementation are the following.

Sobol search (`search_option = 5`). The next prescribed number of points of a Sobol low-discrepancy sequence in $[0, 1]^n$ are generated, converted to canonical states, and evaluated if not already cached.

Pairwise coordinate exchange (`search_option = 6`). The active points are sorted by objective value and the top- k are kept (default $k = 5$). For each pair (ξ^a, ξ^b) the coordinates on which they differ are identified and, starting from the better point, replaced one at a time by their values in the second point, each intermediate canonical state being emitted as a candidate; this yields at most $n \binom{k}{2}$ candidates.

Structural one-point crossover (`search_option = 7`). For each pair among the top- k active points, the canonical vector is cut at structural positions—the end of the categorical block, the end of the ordered discrete block, and the midpoint of the variable vector, whenever these cuts are valid—and for each cut two candidates are generated by exchanging suffixes between the two parent states. This is the search option used in the headline Cat-Suite configuration 2207.

Combined recombination (`search_option = 8`). The combined variant applies both pairwise coordinate exchange and structural one-point crossover to the same selected active set.

The implementation also retains legacy options based on Latin hypercube sampling, random sampling, 2^n -centers grids, and Halton sequences; only the deterministic options

above are used in the reported configurations. For fixed initialization, DNR schedule, active list, and parameters, options 5–8 introduce no random choices and therefore preserve reproducibility. Options 6–8 may be viewed as deterministic recombination search steps: they borrow the information-sharing principle of recombination—elite top- k parent selection, suffix exchange, and progressive component transfer between two good solutions—but remove stochastic parent selection, random cut points, mutation probabilities, and population sampling.

D Worked examples

This appendix records only the worked examples of the poll set $P(\xi^*; \alpha)$ of (13) needed to make the algorithmic construction self-contained. Full raw experiment traces are not inlined in the manuscript; they are released through the accompanying repository.

D.1 Continuous-only specialization

If $n_D = n_K = 0$, the canonical state is $\xi = y \in [0, 1]^{n_C}$ and the mixed poll reduces to the GLODS-SI coordinate poll, the limiting case of Remark 1. For $n_C = 3$, $y^* = (0.40, 0.60, 0.20)$, and $\alpha = 0.10$, the complete poll set consists of the six candidates

$$\begin{aligned} &(0.50, 0.60, 0.20), & (0.30, 0.60, 0.20), \\ &(0.40, 0.70, 0.20), & (0.40, 0.50, 0.20), \\ &(0.40, 0.60, 0.30), & (0.40, 0.60, 0.10), \end{aligned}$$

with projection onto $[0, 1]$ applied to any coordinate that would leave the box.

D.2 Categorical-only specialization

If $n_C = n_D = 0$, the state consists only of categorical identities $\xi = h = (h_1, \dots, h_{n_K})$. For three categorical variables with $m_i = 5$ and a step size giving $r_i = 1$, the poll changes one categorical identity at a time to its forward or backward neighbor in the current active permutation, producing the six candidates

$$\begin{aligned} &(\nu_1(h_1^*, +1), h_2^*, h_3^*), & (\nu_1(h_1^*, -1), h_2^*, h_3^*), \\ &(h_1^*, \nu_2(h_2^*, +1), h_3^*), & (h_1^*, \nu_2(h_2^*, -1), h_3^*), \\ &(h_1^*, h_2^*, \nu_3(h_3^*, +1)), & (h_1^*, h_2^*, \nu_3(h_3^*, -1)). \end{aligned}$$

For this step size, the poll is a rank-one categorical neighborhood, but the meaning of rank-one changes across epochs as the DNR permutations rotate, as illustrated next.

D.3 Permutation rotation: same canonical state, different active neighbors

The defining feature of DNR is that the active permutation rotates across epochs while the canonical category index remains the cache key. Consider a categorical variable with $m = 5$ levels at canonical state $h^* = 3$ and rank $r = 1$.

At epoch e . Let the active permutation be $p^{(e)} = (3, 1, 5, 2, 4)$. The position of h^* is recovered by inverse lookup, $j = (p^{(e)})^{-1}(3) = 1$ (since $p^{(e)}[1] = 3$), and the rank-1 neighbors are read by cyclic stepping,

$$\nu(3, +1) = p^{(e)}[2] = 1, \quad \nu(3, -1) = p^{(e)}[5] = 4.$$

The poll tests the active neighbor set $\{1, 4\}$ in this epoch.

At epoch $e + 1$. The schedule rotates the permutation to $p^{(e+1)} = (5, 3, 1, 4, 2)$. The same canonical state $h^* = 3$ now sits at position $j' = (p^{(e+1)})^{-1}(3) = 2$, and the rank-1 neighbors become

$$\nu(3, +1) = p^{(e+1)}[3] = 1, \quad \nu(3, -1) = p^{(e+1)}[1] = 5.$$

The poll now tests $\{1, 5\}$.

Canonical invariance and cache validity. The canonical category index $h^* = 3$ is unchanged across epochs; only its position in the active permutation changes. Previously evaluated points therefore remain valid in the cache across permutation rotations, while the set of neighbors explored by the poll evolves with the schedule.

D.4 Fully mixed example

Consider one variable of each type, $\xi^* = (y_1^*, k_2^*, h_3^*) = (0.25, 5, 4)$, at step size $\alpha = 0.60$, with the ordered discrete variable having $N_2 = 21$ levels and the categorical variable having $m_3 = 7$ levels and active permutation $p_3^{(e)} = (4, 1, 6, 2, 7, 5, 3)$. The unified rank rule (11) gives

$$r_2 = \max\{1, \text{round}(0.60(21-1))\} = 12, \quad r_3 = \min\{\lfloor 7/2 \rfloor, \max(1, \text{round}(0.60(7-1)))\} = 3,$$

where the categorical cap $\lfloor m_3/2 \rfloor = 3$ is now *active*: the uncapped value $\text{round}(0.60 \times 6) = 4$ is reduced to 3, in contrast to Example 1, where the cap is inactive. The six poll candidates are

$$\begin{aligned} (\Pi_{[0,1]}(0.25 + 0.60), 5, 4) &= (0.85, 5, 4), & (\Pi_{[0,1]}(0.25 - 0.60), 5, 4) &= (0.00, 5, 4), \\ (0.25, \text{clamp}(5 + 12, 1, 21), 4) &= (0.25, 17, 4), & (0.25, \text{clamp}(5 - 12, 1, 21), 4) &= (0.25, 1, 4), \\ (0.25, 5, \nu_3(4, +3)) &= (0.25, 5, 2), & (0.25, 5, \nu_3(4, -3)) &= (0.25, 5, 7). \end{aligned}$$

The first pair are continuous normalized steps (the negative direction clamped to the lower boundary $y_1 = 0$, since $0.25 - 0.60 < 0$), the second pair ordered discrete rank moves with clamping (the negative direction clamped to $k_2 = 1$, since $5 - 12 < 1$), and the third pair categorical permutation-induced moves at the capped rank $r_3 = 3$ (the canonical category $h_3^* = 4$ sits at position $j = 1$ in $p_3^{(e)}$, so $\nu_3(4, +3) = p_3^{(e)}[4] = 2$ and $\nu_3(4, -3) = p_3^{(e)}[5] = 7$). The single step-size parameter α drives all three operators simultaneously; this is the full mixed poll of Example 1, here with the categorical cap active.

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